

ANALYSIS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF MECHANICAL STIRRERS USED IN BIOTECHNOLOGICAL PRODUCTION

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Abstract: Mechanical stirrers are a fundamental component in numerous industrial processes, ensuring effective mixing, heat and mass transfer, and the suspending of various substances. This article presents an in-depth analysis of the design characteristics and operating principles of the main types of mechanical stirring devices. Their application and specific requirements are examined across four key sectors: the food, chemical, pharmaceutical, and biotechnological industries. Emphasis is put on the impact of impeller blade geometry on the process efficiency, final product quality, and energy consumption. Practical examples are provided, and current trends in the development of mixing technologies are discussed.

Keywords: mechanical stirrers, mixing, stirrer geometry, mixing efficiency, energy consumption.

АНАЛИЗ И ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ НА МЕХАНИЧНИ БЪРКАЧКИ С ПРИЛОЖЕНИЕ В БИОТЕХНОЛОГИЧНИТЕ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА

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Резюме: Механичните бъркачки са фундаментален елемент в множество индустриални процеси, осигурявайки ефективно смесване, топло- и масопренос и суспендиране на различни вещества. Тази статия представя задълбочен анализ на конструктивните характеристики и принципите на действие на основните типове механични разбъркващи устройства. Разгледано е тяхното приложение и специфичните изисквания в четири ключови сектора: хранително-вкусовата, химическата, фармацевтичната и биотехнологичната промишленост. Акцент е поставен върху влиянието на геометрията на лопатките на бъркачката, върху ефективността на процесите, качеството на крайния продукт и енергийната консумация. Представени са примери от практиката и са дискутирани съвременни тенденции в развитието на технологиите на разбъркване.

Ключови думи: механични бъркачки, разбъркване, геометрия на бъркачки, ефективност на разбъркване, енергийна консумация.

Introduction

Biotechnological production relies significantly on effective mixing and agitation to ensure optimal conditions for a variety of processes. Mechanical stirrers are devices used to create controlled motion in liquid or semi-liquid media with the aim of achieving homogenisation, dissolution, and suspending of solid particles, dispersion of liquids, and enhancement of heat and mass transfer processes. Their importance is undeniable across a wide range of industrial applications, including the production of food and beverages, pharmaceuticals, polymers, paints, cosmetics, as well as in biotechnological processes, such as fermentation and cell cultures. The proper selection and design of a stirrer is a critical factor in optimising production processes, ensuring product quality, and minimising energy consumption. The specific requirements of different biotechnological applications necessitate a careful analysis of stirrer characteristics and their interaction with biological systems (Asenov, 1990).

This article aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the main types of mechanical stirrers, to examine their structural features and principles of operation, and to explore the specific requirements and applications in the food, chemical, and biotechnological industries (Kolarov, 2003).

Liquid Flow in Vessels with Agitators

The agitator, positioned within the vessel containing the liquid, transfers the inertia from the motor to the liquid, thereby inducing its movement and enabling mixing. This transfer of inertia is due to the pressure exerted by the agitator blades on the liquid. As a result of this motion, a portion of the liquid flows

around the edge of the impeller and mixes with the surrounding fluid, which begins to rotate in the direction of the agitator's rotation. A low-pressure zone forms behind the blade, causing liquid from the surrounding area to be drawn in. Due to the flow and suction effects, turbulent vortices appear near the blades.

As the liquid rotates, centrifugal forces arise, causing the fluid to move radially from the impeller periphery toward the vessel walls, while simultaneously being drawn toward the centre of the impeller. The fluid flow within the vessel, induced by the agitator, is characterised by streamlining (Pанев et al., 1966). Depending on the direction of the currents, there are three main types of flow: tangential, radial, and axial (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Main types of flow

• Axial Flow

- The liquid moves parallel to the axis of rotation of the agitator (either downward or upward).
- Typical for propeller-shaped, helical, and other energy-efficient impeller designs.
- Provides effective displacement of large fluid volumes and is often used for homogenisation and heat exchange.

● **Radial Flow**

- The liquid is expelled perpendicular to the axis of rotation.
- Common in turbine agitators.
- Produces high shear forces, suitable for gas dispersion or solid particle suspending.

● **Tangential Flow**

- The liquid moves in a circular trajectory around the axis of rotation.
- Predominates when there are insufficient guiding elements (baffles), or in low-viscosity fluids.
- May lead to the formation of a vortex effect, which is undesirable in certain processes.

The mechanical agitator, placed in the centre of the vessel, induces the rotational movement of the entire liquid volume, which results in a centrifugal force. In this case, the free surface of the liquid takes the shape of a paraboloid of revolution. At low rotational speeds, a slight depression of the liquid level near the shaft is observed. As the rotational speed increases, the resulting vortex gradually deepens and can reach the stirring device. To prevent vortex formation, or to reduce its depth, vertical baffles (1) are installed in the vessel (Fig. 2). In this figure, the solid line represents the vortex formed in the absence of baffles, while the dashed line shows the reduced vortex depth when baffles are present (Nevenkin et al.,1995).

Fig. 2. Formation of a vortex in a vessel with an agitator

Flow Regime (Reynolds Number, Re)

The Reynolds number (Re) is a dimensionless quantity used in fluid mechanics to determine the type of fluid flow: laminar, transitional, or turbulent. It represents the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces within the fluid. Inertial forces are related to the motion of the fluid, while viscous forces arise from internal friction within the fluid. It is defined by the following formula:

$$Re = \frac{N \cdot \rho \cdot D^2}{\mu} \tag{1}$$

where:

- N is the rotational speed of the agitator (s⁻¹),
- ρ – fluid density (kg/m³),
- D – diameter of the agitator (m),
- μ – dynamic viscosity (Pa.s).

The Reynolds number (or criterion) is essential for determining the flow regime of the fluid (Fig. 3):

● **Laminar Flow (Re < 2300)**

- The movement is orderly, without intermixing of layers.
- Occurs with viscous fluids and at low velocities.
- Mixing is primarily based on molecular diffusion.

● **Transitional Flow (2300 < Re < 10,000)**

- Partially developed turbulence.
- Mixing improves due to the disruption of laminar layers.

● **Turbulent Flow (Re > 10,000)**

- The flow is chaotic, with rapid and efficient mixing.
- Main mixing mechanism: energetic breakup of fluid volumes.

Fig. 3. Fluid flow regimes

Main Types of Mechanical Agitators for Biotechnological Applications and Their Characteristics

Various types of mechanical mixing device are used in biotechnological reactors, differing in their geometry, flow generation method, and application. Some of the most commonly used types include:

Propeller Agitators: These consist of one or more blades mounted on a shaft. They primarily generate axial flow, directed parallel to the shaft. They are effective for mixing low-viscosity liquids and for suspending solid particles at low concentrations. Propeller agitators are often used in smaller bioreactors. This type of agitator (Fig. 4) is efficient in situations where significant liquid circulation is required within the vessel, while keeping mechanical energy consumption to a minimum (Decheva et al., 2013).

Fig. 4. Propeller agitators

Turbine Agitators: These are characterised by flat or curved blades mounted radially on the shaft (Fig. 5). They generate a strong radial flow that is directed toward the vessel walls and then returns to the center. Turbine agitators are suitable for mixing higher-viscosity liquids, liquid–liquid dispersion, and intensive heat transfer. Variants include flat-blade turbines (Rushton turbine), pitched-blade turbines, and others (Kraychev & Yordanov, 2003).

Fig. 5. Turbine agitators

Anchor and Frame Agitators: The shape of these agitators matches the contour of the vessel bottom and walls, with minimal clearance. This type primarily generates tangential flow and is effective for mixing high-viscosity liquids and preventing material buildup on the vessel walls (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Anchor and frame agitators

Spiral (Helical) Agitators: These consist of a helical ribbon mounted on a shaft. They generate axial flow with minimal turbulence, making them suitable for mixing very high-viscosity liquids and sensitive materials (Kraychev & Yordanov, 2003).

Specialised Agitators: This category includes various designs optimised for specific applications, such as agitators for emulsification, aeration, or operation under high pressure and temperature (Zhelyazkov, 1975).

The main characteristics determining the effectiveness of mechanical agitators include:

- **Agitator geometry:** Diameter, number, and shape of blades, blade pitch angle.
- **Rotational speed:** Determines mixing intensity and power consumption.
- **Agitator positioning in the vessel:** Height from the bottom, number of agitators on the shaft.

- **Presence of baffles:** Improves turbulence and prevents vortex formation, especially with turbine agitators.
- **Fluid viscosity:** Significantly affects the flow regime (laminar or turbulent) and the required power input.
- **Density of the fluid and the suspended particles:** Influences the efficiency of suspending and mixing.
- **Energy efficiency:** Minimisation of power consumption.
- **Use of empirical correlations, numerical simulations** (Computational Fluid Dynamics – CFD Fluent 6.0), **and experimental studies** for optimising the design and operating parameters of the mixing system (Sendov et al., 1994).

Application of Mechanical Agitators in Industry

In the food and beverage industry, mechanical agitators are used in a wide range of processes, including the mixing of ingredients, heat transfer, suspending, emulsification, aeration, and more.

The chemical and pharmaceutical industries are also major users of mechanical agitators, which are employed in various processes, such as reaction operations, dissolution, suspending, dispersion, heat and mass transfer.

Biotechnological production represents a specific area where mechanical agitators play a key role in processes, such as fermentation, cell cultures, and biocatalysts (Chisti, 1999).

Several key characteristics and operating parameters determine the efficiency of mechanical agitators:

- **Mixing efficiency:** The ability of the stirring device to create a homogeneous environment in the reactor within a certain period and with specific energy consumption.
- **Mass transfer:** Particularly important in aerobic processes, where the agitator facilitates the dissolution of oxygen in the liquid phase and its transfer to the microorganisms or cells. The mass transfer coefficient ($k_L a$) is a key parameter.
- **Heat transfer:** Maintaining an optimal temperature is critical for biological processes. The agitator contributes to the uniform distribution of heat within the reactor.
- **Shear rate:** The mechanical shear created by the rotation of the agitator can be both beneficial (e.g. for cell disruption) and detrimental (e.g. to sensitive cells). The shear level must be carefully controlled.
- **Energy consumption:** Energy efficiency is an important factor for the cost-effectiveness of biotechnological processes. Different types of agitators have varying energy demands to achieve a pre-set level of mixing.
- **Construction materials:** Agitators are typically made of stainless steel or other biocompatible materials that do not interact with the culture medium or the products (Kolarov, 2003).

Energy Consumption during Mixing

The process of liquid mixing depends on the shape and dimensions of the vessel and the stirrer, the rotation speed of the stirrer, and the physical properties of the liquid. The power required to drive a mechanical stirrer is a key parameter in the design and operation of processes involving the mixing of liquids, suspensions, or emulsions. It directly affects the

efficiency of mixing, homogenisation, dispersion, heat transfer, and other related processes (Nienow, 1997).

The main factors affecting mixing power are:

- **Fluid viscosity:** For low-viscosity liquids (such as water or low-concentration solutions), power is mainly determined by inertial forces and is proportional to the square or cube of the stirrer's rotational speed.

With high-viscosity liquids (such as polymer solutions or suspensions), viscous forces become dominant, and the power is linearly proportional to the stirrer speed.

- **Fluid density:** Fluid density influences inertial forces and, therefore, the power requirement, especially under turbulent operating conditions.

- **Stirrer geometry:**

-Type of stirrer: Different types of stirrers (e.g., anchor, turbine, propeller, helical) generate different hydrodynamic fields and require varying amounts of power to achieve a specific level of mixing.

-Stirrer diameter: Power is generally proportional to the fifth power of the stirrer diameter in turbulent regimes. Larger stirrers require significantly more power to operate at the same speed.

-Number and shape of blades: The number and shape of the blades influence the generated turbulence and shear forces, which in turn affect the required power.

- **Vessel geometry:**

-Vessel diameter: The ratio between the stirrer diameter and the vessel diameter is an important factor. Larger vessels require more power to ensure adequate mixing.

-Liquid height: The height of the liquid affects hydrostatic pressure and fluid circulation.

-Presence of baffles: Baffles in the vessel prevent the formation of a rotating vortex and improve vertical mixing; however, they may also increase the required power.

- **Stirrer rotational speed:** Power is highly dependent on the stirrer speed. Under turbulent flow conditions, power is proportional to the cube of the rotational speed, while under laminar flow, it is proportional to the square of the speed (Joshi et al., 2004).

To characterise the mixing regime and determine the required power, dimensionless numbers and coefficients are used (Kraychev, 2014):

-Reynolds number for mixing (Re): This determines the flow regime (laminar, transitional, turbulent)

-Power coefficient (N_p or K_N): A dimensionless coefficient that depends on the geometry of the stirrer and vessel, as well as on the Reynolds number. It is determined experimentally or through empirical correlations (Hosseini et al., 2016).

- **Calculation of mixing power (P):**

$$P = K_N \cdot \rho \cdot N^3 \cdot D^5 \quad (2)$$

where:

P is the power (W),

K_N – power coefficient,

ρ – fluid density (kg/m³),

N – stirrer rotational speed (s⁻¹),

D – stirrer diameter (m).

- **Power coefficient (K_N) in mixing:** A dimensionless quantity that relates the power consumed by the stirrer to the fluid density, stirrer speed, and stirrer diameter, as well as the flow regime defined by the Reynolds number (Kraychev et al., 2004). It is a key parameter in the design and analysis of processes involving mechanical mixing (Kraychev, 2020). It is calculated using the formula:

$$K_N = \frac{P}{\rho \cdot N^3 \cdot D^5} \quad (3)$$

where:

P is the power (W),

ρ – fluid density (kg/m³),

N – stirrer rotational speed (s⁻¹),

D – stirrer diameter (m).

Conclusion

Mechanical agitators are an indispensable component in a wide range of industrial processes in the food, chemical, pharmaceutical, and biotechnological industries, providing the necessary conditions for the efficient progress of processes. The variety of stirring devices and their specific characteristics allow for adaptation to different process requirements and fluid properties. The effective selection and design of the mixing system is crucial for optimising production processes, ensuring product quality, and minimising energy consumption. Current trends are focused on increasing energy efficiency, improving hygiene, and developing specialised and intelligent mixing technologies.

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